

Appendix of *Assessing LLMs Responses in the Field of Domestic Sustainability: an Exploratory Study*

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APPENDIX A APPENDIX OF STUDY 1

We report the ten questions used to validate the selected generative models.

A. Question 1

a) *Submitted Question:* Where does all the carbon we release go?

b) *Trustable source:* https://www.ted.com/talks/kristen_bell_giant_ant_where_does_all_the_carbon_we_release_go?referrer=playlist-5_questions_about_climate_change&autoplay=true

c) *Results:* Table I

B. Question 2

a) *Submitted Question:* Why is air pollution a fast-growing concern?

b) *Trustable source:* <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2018/nov/05/air-pollution-everything-you-should-know-about-a-public-health-emergency>

c) *Results:* Table II

C. Question 3

a) *Submitted Question:* Climate crisis linked to at least 15 \$1bn-plus disasters in 2019. What are the costs of floods, fires and storms around the world?

b) *Trustable source:* <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/dec/27/climate-crisis-linked-to-at-least-15-1bn-plus-disasters-in-2019>

c) *Results:* Table III

D. Question 4

a) *Submitted Question:* Should we worry about 8 billion people?

b) *Trustable source:* <https://www.hcn.org/articles/landline-should-we-worry-about-8-billion-people>

c) *Results:* Table IV

E. Question 5

a) *Submitted Question:* What are the biggest environmental problems of 2021? (Give me 11 problems and a possible solution for each of them)

b) *Trustable source:* <https://earth.org/drawn-up-biggest-environmental-problems-of-2021/>

c) *Results:* Table V

F. Question 6

a) *Submitted Question:* What are five big ways the United States will need to adapt to climate change?

b) *Trustable source:* <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/11/26/climate/adaptation-us-climate-change.html>

c) *Results:* Table VI

G. Question 7

a) *Submitted Question:* Why do some cities tend to get more rain than their surrounding countryside?

b) *Trustable source:* <https://www.snexplores.org/article/warming-cities-may-see-more-rain-and-frequent-flooding>

c) *Results:* Table VII

H. Question 8

a) *Submitted Question:* How to limit the need for pesticides?

b) *Trustable source:* <https://www.snexplores.org/article/how-limit-need-pesticides>

c) *Results:* Table VIII

I. Question 9

a) *Submitted Question:* In the future will air conditioning be a big problem for environmental and social aspects?

b) *Trustable source:* <https://www.ilpost.it/2021/08/14/aria-condizionata/>

c) *Results:* Table IX

J. Question 10

a) *Submitted Question:* *Are biodegradable items or packaging easy to dispose of?*

b) *Trustable source:* <https://www.ilpost.it/2020/10/05/differenza-materiali-biodegradabili-compostabili/>

c) *Results:* Table X

TABLE I
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION ONE

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	LLama
Original source	✓	7	0	7	5
Atmosphere cycle	✓	6	5	6	6
Human carbon production	✓	7	0	2	7
Solutions to reduce carbon	✓	3	6	2	3
Global warming	✓	5	0	0	5
Why carbon is necessary		1	2	4	0

TABLE II
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION TWO

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Health effects	✓	8	7	7	7
Cost	✓	1	0	2	3
Who is affected by this	✓	6	3	4	2
Different types of air pollution	✓	0	1	6	5
Indoor air pollution	✓	2	1	5	4
Dangers of toxic air	✓	3	7	7	6
Self protection	✓	6	2	6	7
Causes		8	5	3	5
Government action		4	0	0	1
Risk of COVID-19		4	5	0	0

TABLE III
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION THREE

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Cyclone Idai	✓	6	5	7	6
Cyclone Fani	✓	1	1	6	5
Storm Eberhard	✓		1	2	0
Typhoon Faxai	✓		2	6	4
Hurricane Dorian	✓	4	6	5	6
Hurricane Harvey		4	2	4	1
Typhoon Hagibis		5	6	7	7
Australian bushfires		6	2	6	7
Floods in Iran		4	1	2	2
California wildfires		1	5	3	3

TABLE IV
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION FOUR

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Increasing demand in food, water and energy	✓	7	7	7	6
Consumption patterns	✓	5	4	5	5
Technology and efficiency	✓	4	2	3	3
Environmental policies	✓	5	2	5	4
Overpopulation	✓	7	5	6	7
Food waste	✓	6	7	6	5
Pollution	✓	1	5	2	3
Deforestation	✓	1	5	5	4
Climate change		3	6	0	6

TABLE V
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION FIVE

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Poor governance	✓	2	5	1	3
Food waste	✓	2	6	6	7
Biodiversity loss	✓	6	5	5	5
Plastic pollution	✓	7	6	5	5
Deforestation	✓	7	6	7	7
Air pollution	✓	7	3	7	5
Agriculture	✓	1	5	4	3
Global warming from fossil fuels	✓	3	4	1	1
Melting ice caps	✓	2	0	6	0
Sea level rise	✓	2	1	6	0
Food and water insecurity	✓	5	0	5	1
Climate change		7	3	7	4
Ocean pollution		7	5	4	1
Land degradation		6	0	2	0
Ocean acidification		5	1	0	0
Soil erosion		5	2	3	0
Nuclear waste		6	1	1	0
Water pollution		2	4	6	2
Natural resource failing		2	6	2	0
Desertification		1	5	6	6
Atmosphere pollution		3	6	5	5

TABLE VI
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION SIX

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Farming reengineering	✓	7	7	7	6
Build for the future	✓	6	6	6	5
Retreat from the coast	✓	6	5	4	2
Enlist nature to help	✓	1	3	1	1
Adapt to unexpected events	✓	1	0	6	0
Environment health		7	5	0	5
Renewable energy		8	4	1	7
Manage water resources		0	6	1	1

TABLE VII
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION SEVEN

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Urban rain effect	✓	2	6	5	5
Heat islands	✓	7	5	7	5
Unstable air circulation in hotter cities	✓	4	5	0	0
Tall buildings channel hot air up	✓	2	0	0	0
Pollution as aerosol as seed for droplets		1	0	3	0
Storm splitting	✓	2	0	0	0
Topography		5	0	0	0
Lack of stormwater system maintenance	✓	2	2	2	0
Role of green areas and trees	✓	3	1	3	1
Flood prevention: green areas, slow the floods, rain gardens	✓	3	2	3	0
Early warning systems for floods		2	0	0	0
Education		2	0	1	2

TABLE VIII
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION EIGHT

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Kids safety	✓	1	0	1	0
Reduce pesticide exposure	✓	6	5	7	6
Pest management	✓	7	4	7	7
Release ladybugs	✓	2	4	3	4
Allelopathy	✓	0	0	0	0
Crop rotation		7	6	6	7
Natural pest killers		5	0	4	3

TABLE IX
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION NINE

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Energy consumption	✓	8	5	7	6
Pollution	✓	7	6	7	7
Global warming	✓	7	0	6	4
Economic problems	✓	5	0	3	0
Better life quality	✓	1	1	0	0
Resources access disparity	✓	5	0	5	0
Environmental impact		7	1	7	3
Solutions		8	4	6	1

TABLE X
EXAMPLE OF TOPIC EXTRACTION AND COUNTING FOR QUESTION TEN

Topic	Trustable source	ChatGPT	BingAI	Bard	OpenAssistant (LLama)
Pollution from bio disposal	✓	8	5	4	4
Difference between compostable and biodegradable	✓	1	0	4	0
Disposal times of bio and compostable	✓	7	0	3	5
Research on new technologies	✓	1	2	6	6
Disposal processes	✓	8	1	5	0

APPENDIX B
FIRST QUESTIONNAIRE

What are your three biggest doubts in the area of eco-sustainability? Please enter each one in the form of a question inside the following boxes. E.g. What is offside in soccer?

- Question 1
- Question 2
- Question 3

APPENDIX C
SECOND FORM

A. *Question 1*

- Category: Reducing plastic use
- Question: How do you throw away a plastic bottle with a cap?
- Answer: To properly dispose of a plastic bottle with a cap, empty the contents, crush the bottle to reduce its volume, screw the cap on, and throw it in the plastic recycling container. Remember to follow your municipality's specific rules for recycling collection.

B. *Question 2*

- Category: Concerns about the environment and related actions
- Question: Why only Europe will stop producing thermal engine cars in 2035?
- Answer: Europe has set a target to reduce CO2 emissions to tackle climate change. In 2020, it imposed new emissions regulations on electric cars and plug-in hybrids, and the goal is to eliminate thermal engine cars completely by 2035. Other countries may have similar goals, but Europe is leading the change in this area.

C. *Question 3*

- Category: Environmental policies
- Question: How much is the actual difference in terms of environmental impact between an all plant-based diet and an omnivorous diet?
- Answer: A completely plant-based diet has significantly less environmental impact than an omnivorous diet. Meat production requires large amounts of water, land and food, creating greenhouse gas emissions and deforestation. In addition, meat consumption is associated with health problems such as cardiovascular disease and obesity. Switching to a plant-based diet can significantly reduce environmental impact and improve personal health.

D. *Question 4*

- Category: Greenwashing and "green" solutions
- Question: How to sustain complete transition to green from an energy perspective?
- Answer: To sustain the complete transition to green from an energy perspective, it is necessary to invest in renewable energy production such as solar, eolic, hydropower, geothermal, and bio-mass. In addition, it is necessary to reduce energy consumption through energy efficiency

and promote the adoption of sustainable practices such as public transportation, electric mobility, and eco-friendly construction. It is also important to raise people's awareness about the importance of sustainability and create incentives for the use of renewable energy sources.

E. *Question 5*

- Category: Eco-sustainability and sustainable behaviors
- Question: Is it possible to make the production of hardware components environmentally sustainable?
- Answer: Yes, hardware manufacturing can become environmentally sustainable through the adoption of sustainable practices such as the use of renewable energy, recyclable materials, efficient manufacturing processes, and innovative technologies. However, this requires sustained efforts by companies, governments and consumers to reduce the environmental impact of the hardware industry.

F. *Question 6*

- Category: Energy and environmental impact
- Question: How to reduce the CO2 that I produce?
- Answer: In order to reduce the CO2 produced, you can take several actions, such as using eco-friendly transportation, reducing energy consumption at home, choosing products with a low carbon footprint, eating less meat and increasing consumption of local and seasonal food, as well as offsetting emissions through forestation projects or purchasing carbon credits.

G. *Question 7*

- Category: Environmental sustainability
- Question: Does it pollute more a car with a thermal engine or the disposal of an electric car battery?
- Answer: The car with a thermal engine pollutes more than the production and disposal of an electric car battery. Combustion cars emit harmful substances into the air, such as nitrogen oxides and particulate matter, contributing to air pollution. On the other hand, the production and disposal of electric batteries have an environmental impact, but efforts to improve the sustainability of battery production and recycling are reducing this impact in the long term.